

STUDY OF THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *STAR-ANISE.*

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The fatty oil contains the following percentages of acids: myristic, 4.43; stearic, 7.93; oleic, 63.24; linolic, 24.4. The yield of the oil is 55% on the weight of the decorticated seeds.

Star-anise (*N. ()*, Magnoliaceae) comprises several ever-green aromatic shrubs with coriaceous leaves, readily known by the arrangement of the one-sided carpels in one radiating whorl. When ripe, they are woody and split at the upturned ventral suture so that the seeds become visible. The carpels are used as an ingredient in curry powder, but the seeds are usually thrown away.

The present study deals with the fatty oil obtained from the seeds of the variety, obtained locally from the bazaar, and known as "badamful," and identified as *I. verum*. It is imported from China. A preliminary note on the subject appeared previously (*Current Sci.*, 1939, 8, 388).

It should be noted that Bulir (*Z. Nahr. Genussem*, 1912, 24, 309) has also studied the oils from two varieties of *Illicium*. His results are summarised below along with our results.

TABLE I.

	<i>I. ocrum</i> (Bulir).	<i>I. religiosum</i> (Bulir).	Badamful (<i>I. verum</i>). Authors.
Yield	20%	12.5%	55%
Iodine value	93.1	90.6	88.36
Sap. value	193.8	193.4	194.5
Liquid acids	68.9%	70.0%	87.64%
Solid acids	25.8%	25%	12.36%
Oleic acid	45.0%	60.2%	63.24%
Linolic acid	23.9%	9.8%	24.4%
Palmitic acid	23.2%	22.5%	—
Stearic acid	2.6%	2.5%	7.93%
Myristic acid	—	—	4.43%

From the above table it appears that the oils Bulir has studied were quite different from each other as well as from the one we have studied. One of the oils obtained by Bulir had a fluorescence and both of them were yellow in colour. Our oil was reddish yellow in colour and had no fluorescence. Further, the figures for total solid fatty acids obtained by Bulir from the two oils are almost double of what we found in our oil. Even the composition is quite different. He finds no myristic acid in his oils whereas we find no palmitic acid in our oil.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The seeds were first decorticated, crushed and then extracted with petroleum ether in a Soxhlet apparatus, the ether from the extracted oil being removed by distillation, and the last traces by distillation under vacuum.

The oil has no particular taste. Its appearance is reddish yellow. Its physical and chemical constants are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Yield (on the weight of decorticated seeds)	55%	Sp. gr. at 25°	0·9128
Sap value	194·5	Acetyl number..	8·37
Ref. Index at 25°	1·4677	Reichert-Meissel value	0·75
Iodine value	88·36	Polenske number	0·29
Acid number	11·65	Unsaponifiable matter	0·59%

The Insoluble Fatty Acids.

The oil was saponified with alcoholic potash and then the alcohol was completely distilled off. The soaps obtained were dissolved in large quantities of water and the free fatty acids liberated by the addition of hydrochloric acid. The fatty acids (95%) which floated on the top were washed with water, filtered through a hot water funnel, and dried over calcium chloride. Their constants are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Mixed Fatty Acids.

Yield	95%	Titre value	20°C
Iodine value	99·45	Acid number	203·5
	Mean M. W.	280·6	

Separation of Solid and Liquid Fatty Acids.

The mixed fatty acids were separated into solid and liquid acids by Twitchell's lead salt method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) when their percentages were found to be as follows :

Total mixed acids taken	199.92 g.
Solid acids obtained	23.8 g. (12.36%)
Liquid acids obtained	168.7 g. (87.64%)

The Solid Acids.

The lead salts were decomposed with dilute nitric acid, and the liberated fatty acids were taken up with ether. The ether extract was washed several times with water till the washings were no longer acid to methyl orange. On evaporating the ether, the solid acids were obtained, constants of which are given below.

TABLE IV.

Percentage	12.36	Acid number	215.5
Iodine value	2	Mean M. W.	259.9

Methyl Esters of the Solid Acids.

The solid acids were refluxed for nearly 4 hours with methyl alcohol, saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. The mixture was then poured into water and ether added. The ether extract was washed with a solution of sodium carbonate to remove any unesterified acids, and then after the evaporation of the ether, the esters were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. The details are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

19 G. esters distilled under 2 mm. pressure.

Fraction.	Temp.	Wt.	Sap. value.	Fraction.	Temp.	Wt.	Sap. value.
I	Below 170°	7.89 g.	214.9	IV	180°-185°	1.04 g.	191.7
II	170°-175°	3.3	208	V	185°-200°	1.82	191.7
III	175°-180°	1.82	198.5	VI	Residue	2.68	190.7

In the case of each of these fractions, acids were separated by fractional precipitation, and only myristic and stearic acids were isolated. Each fraction was hydrolysed and the acids obtained were dissolved in dilute acetone, when in each case the acid that crystallised out first, melted at 67-68° and had 281-283 as its molecular weight. The mixed melting point with each other in the case of these samples remained unchanged. Similarly the mixed melting point with an authentic sample of stearic acid remained unchanged. The mother-liquor in the case of each of the fractions yielded an acid melting at 52-53°, the melting point in each case with an authentic sample of myristic acid remaining unchanged. Molecular weight in all these cases was 228. The intermediate fractions were further fractionally crystallised when only these two acids were obtained.

In Table VI are given the calculated proportions, on percentage basis, of these two acids, fraction-wise. Corresponding theoretical saponification values of their methyl esters and mean molecular weights are also given, which compare well with observed values.

TABLE VI.

Frac- tion.	% acids.		S. V of methyl esters.	Mean M.W.	Frac- tion.	% Acids.		S. V. of methyl esters.	Mean M.W.
	Myristic.	Stearic.				Myristic.	Stearic.		
I	50	50	209.7	256	IV	15	85	194.68	275.6
II	40	60	203.54	261.6	V	15	85	194.68	275.6
III	38	62	200.45	263	Residue	10	90	192.5	278.5

Total mean molecular weight calculated here, which is 263, compares well with the one actually observed (259.9). Thus the solid acids are: myristic, 35.8% and stearic, 64.2%.

Bromination of Liquid Acids.

The liquid acids (20 g.) were dissolved in 50 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. Separately bromine was mixed with equal volume of acetic acid, and the two were left in an ice-box for a while. Then the bromine solution was slowly added to the acids with constant shaking, till the colour of bromine persisted. The flask was kept in ice all along.

The flask was then kept in an ice-box overnight, and no solid was obtained. The whole was then poured into cold water and shaken with sodium thiosulphate to remove excess of free bromine. Then after the

removal of water, petroleum ether was added, and the whole mass stirred for a long time. Gradually a solid began to separate. The precipitate was transferred to a weighed filter paper and washed with cold petroleum ether till the filtrate became colourless. The solid bromo derivative was weighed and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $113-14^{\circ}$; the bromine was estimated to be 52.84% . The weight of the bromide was 12.5 g. Ether was removed from the filtrate and again after washing with sodium thiosulphate, it was thoroughly dried. It weighed 22.62 g., and its bromine contents were 35.55% .

TABLE VII.

Acids taken for bromination = 20 g.

Oleic dibromide obtained = 22.62 g. (Found : Br, 35.55% . Calc. Br., 36.28%).

Linolic tetrabromide obtained = 12.5 g (Found : Br, 52.84% . Calc. Br, 53.33%).

Hence

12.5 G of linolic tetrabromide = 5.566 g. linolic acid. 22.62 G. of oleic dibromide = 14.43 g. of oleic acid.

Oleic acid present = 72.15% .

Linolic acid present = 27.83% .

This percentage composition of the liquid acids corresponds well to the iodine value of the mixed liquid acids, and that of the mixed solid and liquid acids already obtained :

Calculated mean iodine value for mixed liquid acids = 115.45

The one actually obtained = 114.5

The I. V. (calc on the basis of 12.36% solid and 87.64% liquid acids) = 101.2

The one actually obtained = 99.45

Hence the percentage of the fatty acid contents of the oil works out as follows : Myristic acid, 4.43 ; oleic acid, 63.24 ; stearic acid, 7.93 ; linolic acid 24.4 . Mean molecular weight calculated according to these figures comes to 279.3 which corresponds well to the observed value, 280.6 .